

SOP

FILTRATION OF AIRBORNE NANO- AND MICROPLASTIC PARTICLES IN CASCADE

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1 Introduction

One of the main challenges that occur in the analysis of small particles, especially for nano- and microplastic particles is contamination during sampling and sample handling. For quantitative analysis, a trustworthy test routine is based on at least two samples: a blank sample for monitoring background contaminations and an analytical sample.

2 Work precautions

To reduce the contamination of the samples during processing several of precautions must be considered:

- a. Use powder-free Nitrile gloves.
- b. Use a lab coat with low content of fibres
- c. Do not lean over the filtration system during mounting/unmounting or during the process.
- d. Do not use stainless-steel tweezers. Si filters are sensitive to scratches. Al_2O_3 is sensitive to the pressure of the tweezers.
- e. Do not use any equipment containing plastics or other polymers.
- f. Use only Teflon or Teflon-covered tweezers.
- g. **IMPORTANT:** Filters should be used in the same position as they are delivered. Depending on the fabrication process of the filters the back side can be very rough and the analysis of the samples afterwards difficult. (Si: black side = topside)
- h. Avoid contact with tension. All materials are highly conductive. Avoid also electrostatic charges (in the weighing lab, garment etc.)
- i. Do not let the sample open before or after the experiment.
- j. Do not bend the samples, sensitive filters can crash.
- k. When handling particles $<1 \mu\text{m}$, please also make sure to use an FFP3 respiratory mask.

3 Workflow

The workflow for microplastic analysis can be divided into the following three steps: sample preparation, filtration procedure and detection of the microplastics.

This SOP addresses the sample preparation and filtration procedure for airborne nano and microplastic particles.

3.1 Sample preparation

The setup for the experiment on the filtration of nano- and microplastics from the air is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Set-up for airborne nano- and microplastic experiments: 1 multitool, 2- vacuum adapters, 3- bottom protection screws, 4- top protection screws, 5- filter holders, 6- mount screws, 7-filters (Si left and Al₂O₃ right)

Performing the blank sampling filtration routine is mandatory to monitor influences of handling and contamination from laboratory/factory and filtration equipment. Blank filtration should be performed in a clean atmosphere, such as a glovebox, clean laboratory, or clean room.

Blank samples are measured in CSP in a clean atmosphere under same parameters and equipment as the experiments made in the factory.

3.2 Filtration procedure

A video example of the filtration procedure can be seen on the webpage siliziumfiler.de

Before starting the experiments, the filters should be weight individually. The data should be documented in an excel file as presented in Table 1.

Sample_ID	Material	Filter	Filter Poresize [µm]	Date Sampling	Initial weight [mg]	Weight after sampling [mg]	Material weight [mg]	LUMI	SEM	µ-FT-IR	µ-Raman	TED-GC/MS	Notes
PR_INCDTL_1	PET	Si	10	01.12.2022			0,00						

Table 1. Table head for sampling with important information about sampling

This procedure should be made in clean lab or in a glovebox to reduce the contamination of the filters. Put the clean weighed filter in the filter holder, which will also be the transport cell.

The transport system is presented in Fig.2. One filter is put in one filter holder. If more filters should be transported, combine as many filters holder as needed with one filter per holder. The filters in the filter holders (5) are fixed with mount screws (6). Cautions: when manipulating the filtration/transport system do not interchange the filter holders if there is more than one. The cascade system should have the filters with the largest pore size in the first position followed by other filters with decreasing pore size.

Figure 2. Filtration/Transport system consists only one filter holder, the top cup and the bottom cup. For more filters only the number of filter holders is different

If only one filter holder (5) is used, unscrew the top protection screw (3) and the bottom protection screw (4). In the case of using a cascade system with more than one filter holder (as in fig. 2) unscrew the top protection screw (3) and the first holder (5). Screw back the top protection screw (3) on the further transport system to protect against contamination. Position the filter holder in a vertical position. Insert the multitool (1) in the upper part of the filter holder to unscrew the mounting screw (6). Position the mounting screw on the table and fix the multitool as shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Positioning the multitool on the mount screw.

Carefully insert the filter holder (5) in the multitool (1). By this operation, the filter will be lifted on the top part of the multitool and easy to get using tweezers as presented in Fig.4. Remove the filter from the filter holder. Weight the filter again by using a precise balance. The data should be documented in the same excel file as presented in Table 1.

After weighting, the filter will be inserted back into the filter holder in the opposite order as for unmounting. The procedure must be repeated for all filters used in the cascade experiments.

Cautions: The cascade system should have the filters with the largest pore size in the first outer/upper position followed by other filters with decreasing pore size.

After finishing the weighting procedure and the transport system is mounted together including the top and bottom protection cup, the system can be transported to the place, where the sampling experiments take place.

Figure 4. Get the filter from the filter holder using the multitool.

In the sampling place, unscrew the bottom protection screw and replace that with the vacuum adapter (2) as shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5. Change the bottom protection with the vacuum adapter

After change, the adapter of the filtration system can be connected directly to the sampling pump. In the next step, the sampling parameters (e.g. airflow, experiment duration) should be set on the pump. Note the sampling parameters in Table 2. Unscrew about $\frac{3}{4}$ from the screw length of the top protection screw (4). Start the pump and quickly release the top protection screw completely.

Finally, at the end of the sampling screw first the top protection screw (4) and then release the vacuum adapter from the sampling tube. Screw the bottom protection screw (3) and the system can be transported back to the laboratory.

Figure 6. Connect the filter system to the sampling pump.

The experiment parameters should be saved in a table as presented in Table 2.

Parameters	CSP_PREv3
Data Sampling	01.12.2022
Sampling place	Bucharest
Air concentration [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	
Air speed/flow [l/min]	3,00
Air volume [l]	1000,00
Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	25,00
Environment Air Pressure [atm]	1,00
Collection time [h]	6,00

Table 2. Experimental parameters

In the best case, a photo of the filters with the samples will be helpful to be attached to the date only for documentation purposes. After weighing the filters, the transport system should be built and can be sent to other laboratories for the analytical measurements.

In the laboratory, connect the vacuum adapter once more to the air collection pump and start the pump for about 30 sec/ several sec. Release the vacuum adapter from the tube to get back to the normal atmosphere and after that unscrew the top protection screw. With this procedure, the particles that are not attached to the filter and are in the space above the filter are brought back and adhere to the filter for further experiments.

4 References

[1] Hagendorf, C. Richter, S., Krause, S., Bauer J., Miclea, P.-T., Braun, U. et al in ICSEWEN19: <https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-bam/frontdoor/index/index/docId/50006>

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